

BAT ACOUSTIC SURVEY FOR NANTUCKET

ABSTRACT

I conducted a preliminary acoustic study of bats on Nantucket, in order to inventory species present on the island, and to document the persistence of any northern long-eared bats. Bats were surveyed using passive acoustic monitoring at five sites on the eastern part of Nantucket. Silver-haired and hoary bats were recorded beginning in late July and late August respectively, and continuing into October and early November, suggesting use during the fall migration season. Eastern red bats were recorded from May through early November, and appear to be summer residents. The northern long-eared bat, a federally threatened species, was also documented, using both acoustic and physical evidence. Presence of other *Myotis* spp. was suggested by auto-classification software, but could not be confirmed via manual identification. Big brown bats and tricolored bats were also present on at least one site on Nantucket.

INTRODUCTION

Massachusetts is home to nine species of bats, but most face significant threats to their continued survival and persistence in the state. The federally endangered Indiana bat (*Myotis sodalis*), formerly known from Hampden and Berkshire counties, has been absent from the state since 1939. The eastern small-footed bat (*M. leibii*) is rare in Massachusetts, and listed as state - endangered due to disturbances at hibernation sites. Three additional bat species, the northern long-eared bat (*M. septentrionalis*), little brown bat (*M. lucifugus*), and tricolored bat (*Perimyotis subflavus*), were all recently listed as endangered in the state of Massachusetts (MassWildlife 2015), following the outbreak of white nose syndrome (WNS). This fungal disease has led to population reductions of up to 90-100% at hibernation sites in the Northeast (Turner et al. 2011). Given this decline, the northern long-eared bat has also received federal threatened species status (USFWS 2016). While still common in the state, the big brown bat (*Eptesicus fuscus*) has shown dramatic declines associated with the spread of WNS (Turner et al. 2011). Little is known about the population status of the three long-distance migratory bats found in Massachusetts, but these species are at risk at wind facilities, which killed an estimated 600,000 bats in the U.S. in 2012

(Hayes 2013). The hoary bat (*Lasiurus cinereus*), eastern red bat (*Lasiurus borealis*), and silver-haired bat (*Lasionycteris noctivagans*) account for nearly 75% of fatalities at wind farms in the eastern United States (Arnett et al. 2008), and concern is growing that as capacity expands, mortality at wind facilities could become an issue on the population-scale (Cryan 2011).

Given these threats, there is a growing interest in inventorying bat species in the Northeast, and identifying areas which might provide important habitat to bats, or support persistent populations of WNS-affected species. Historic information on bat populations and habitat use on Nantucket is scant, but several lines of indirect evidence suggest the island could provide important habitat for both long-distance migratory bats and rare hibernating species.

First, surveys on Martha's Vineyard and Cape Cod indicate that this region had high numbers of northern long-eared bats (*Myotis septentrionalis*) before the outbreak of white-nose syndrome (WNS) (Buresch 1999, Massachusetts Army National Guard 2000). A follow-up study on Martha's Vineyard in 2014 found that populations had declined, but were still higher than some inland areas pre-WNS (Biodiversity Works 2014, Carl Herzog, personal communication). This stands in contrast to many inland populations of northern long-eared bats, which have virtually disappeared from the landscape. The persistence of northern long-eared bats on Martha's Vineyard and other coastal locations has led to the hypothesis that these bats may be hibernating locally in habitat not conducive to the spread of WNS, rather than travelling to large inland hibernacula (Laura Eaton, personal communication). If true, these persistent populations could be a target for protection and habitat management.

Second, a long anecdotal history suggests migratory bats utilize coastal and offshore areas during their fall migration (Peterson et al. 2014). One early account describes migratory species feeding in the fall in the sparsely vegetated area around the Highland lighthouse on the tip of Cape Cod (Miller 1897). More recently, acoustic studies in the Gulf of Maine documented the presence of bats in coastal regions, on islands, and in the offshore environment on at least 30% of nights in the fall (Peterson et al. 2014). Bats were significantly more likely to be found coastally than inland. In addition, limited surveys and mist-netting efforts on nearby Tuckernuck Island have resulted in capture of several eastern red and silver-haired bats (Richard Veit,

personal communication). Given these findings, it is likely that migratory tree bats are using Nantucket as a stopover site during the fall migration season.

The need for an understanding of bat ecology in this area has become particularly crucial in the context of regional wind development. Nantucket Sound and the Cape Cod region have become a focal area for wind development, particularly development offshore. A strong wind profile and high electricity prices in the region suggest this trend is likely to continue (NREL 2011), despite, in some cases, local opposition. While these facilities pose the greatest risk to long-distance migratory bats, protecting WNS-affected populations from any additional mortality is also critical.

The goals of this study were to 1) inventory bat species present on Nantucket using passive acoustic monitoring, 2) determine if northern long-eared bats are present on the island, and 3) summarize preliminary findings on bat activity relative to habitat and season.

METHODS

Study Sites and Acoustic Detector Deployment

I deployed nine acoustic receiver stations at five study sites on the eastern side of Nantucket (Figure 1). Each station consisted of an Anabat acoustic detector set in a PVC junction box, with the microphone pointed downward into a PVC elbow. All units were powered by a 12-volt battery charged by a small solar panel. Detectors were mounted 1-3 m above ground level, hung from a tree, shrubs or poles set in the ground, as the location allowed. Detectors were set to operate between 6 PM and 8 AM every night. Eight paired stations were deployed at four study sites in late April, with the two stations at each site separated by at least 100 m. Stations were checked periodically throughout the season to download data and ensure proper operation. In mid-August, one station was moved from the Squam Farm site to Gibbs Pond, in order to sample a broader range of habitats. All stations were retrieved on November 13. See Table 1 for a description of station locations.

Bat Call Identification

Nights with an average of 100 calls per hour or greater (>1400 files per night) were ignored during analysis since they were typically associated with windy nights with many noise files and few bat calls. All other files were extracted and viewed using Analook software. Files containing bat calls were analyzed using two auto-classification programs, Echo Class V3.1 (U.S. Army Engineer R&D Center, 2015) and Kaleidoscope Pro (Wildlife Acoustics Inc., 2015). These are the only auto-classification programs approved by the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service for identification of Indiana bats (*Myotis sodalis*) and northern long-eared bats (*M. septentrionalis*) in zero-cross acoustic data.

Bat call files were run through Echo Class software using the Species Set 2 list, which includes only the nine bat species found in Massachusetts. This auto-classification system returns a probability related to the presence of a species at a detector station on a given night. A “-1” value indicates that the species was not detected at a station. A “1” indicates that the species was detected at the station on a given night, but only with a single call sequence. Because auto-classification is an error-prone technology, a single call sequence is not allowed to determine presence. If more than one call sequence is detected at the station, the software returns a maximum likelihood estimate indicating the probability that the presence of a species at a site on a given night was falsely identified. A low p-value therefore indicates a species is likely present at the site.

Bat calls files were also analyzed using the Kaleidoscope Pro auto classifier software. For this classification the software was set to the “0 Balanced” (Neutral) setting, and the Massachusetts region was selected, which includes only the nine bat species found in Massachusetts. This program identifies individual calls to species where possible, and provides attributes of the calls, including duration, critical frequency, and slope at critical frequency. The program also provides a maximum likelihood estimator describing the probability that a species was misidentified at a site. The estimator takes into account two inputs: 1) how many detections of each bat the classifier found, and 2) a confusion matrix representing the known error rates across all classifiers (i.e. how likely is one bat species to be mis-identified as another).

Probable bat calls were also manually identified to genus and species, where possible, using comparison to reference calls provided by Carl Herzog and Trevor Peterson, as well as identification keys (Humboldt State University; Carl Herzog of New York Dept. of Env. Conservation; Douglas A. Keinath of Wyoming Natural Diversity Database). It is important to note that many bat call characteristics are not diagnostic and no dichotomous keys are available; there is often overlap among species, and echoes off of vegetation or other noise in the recording can obscure calls and make them difficult to accurately identify to species. The ability to distinguish calls also varies among species. Hoary bats (*Lasiurus cinereus*) have low-frequency calls that tend to end at or below ~20 kHz, and can thus readily be distinguished from other species. Silver-haired (*Lasionycteris noctivagans*) and big brown (*Eptesicus fuscus*) bats both produce frequency-modulated calls which typically end in the ~25-30 kHz range, but silver-haired bats also produce flat calls at or above 26 kHz, which are diagnostic for this species. Eastern red bats (*Lasiurus borealis*) typically produce calls with a minimum frequency in the 32-38 kHz range. Calls often vary 1-2 kHz between pulses, which can help identify this species. Tricolored bats (*Perimyotis subflavus*) produce frequency-modulated calls which can be difficult to distinguish from those of red bats, but which often end in near-constant frequency tails ~ 42 kHz. Eastern small-footed bats (*Myotis leibii*) have calls that end at 45 kHz or higher. Other *Myotis* species have calls that end in the 38-42 kHz range; these species can best be distinguished from each other by the slope of the call, but there is some overlap. These calls can also be confused with red bat calls, or with the increased slope of other species' calls entering a "feeding buzz." In long call sequences, feeding buzzes can be distinguished by the shortening of intervals between calls, but in shorter call sequences this is not always possible. In sum, manual identification of calls is an inexact science, with accuracy increasing with the experience of the identifier.

Following auto and manual classification, identifications by all three systems were compared call by call. Calls in which auto and manual classification were in agreement were generally considered correct identifications. In cases where auto-classifications could not be made, where manual classifications were not in agreement with auto-classifications, or where few instances of a given species were identified, call files were again reviewed for accuracy of identification. Where there was a lack of defining characteristics, or questions of accuracy, call files were

shared with experts with a greater proficiency and experience in identifying bat calls (Carl Herzog, Trevor Peterson).

Other Survey Methods

A “Got Bats” outreach effort was made through the Nantucket Conservation Foundation blog, requesting information from local residents about any sightings of bats foraging or roosting on the island. This content was also shared on social media.

A list of bat specimens was obtained from the Maria Mitchell Foundation, which maintains a collection of bats found on the island.

RESULTS

Acoustic detectors were deployed at station locations for 80-198 (mean=174) nights between the end of April and mid-November, and successfully recorded during 60-100% (mean=84%) of nights deployed (Table 2). Data was recorded for a total of 1,132 detector-nights. Detector error led to some missed nights, but detectors for the most part functioned throughout the season. There were a total of 70 “noisy” nights, with greater than 1400 files per night. These nights were ignored during analysis, since reviewing files is a time-intensive process, and large numbers of files are typically indicative of windy nights when bats are not likely to be active. The detectors generated over 296,300 files, of which 5,838 contained bat calls. Bat calls were detected throughout the study period, from April 30 through November 11.

Automated classification systems identified bat calls to species at all detector stations. The ability of the software to identify calls to species varied considerably from station to station, but Kaliedoscope was consistently less conservative, identifying more calls at every site (Table 3). Both automated systems appeared to be more likely to identify calls from eastern red, silver-haired, and hoary bats to species, with fewer identifications made of high frequency calls likely generated by *Myotis* species.

Species Presence – EchoClass

EchoClass software identified all three long-distance migratory bats (eastern red bats, silver-haired bats, hoary bats) as present at acoustic stations on Nantucket, with a probability that these species were mis-identified of $p < 0.01$. Red bats were the most common bat positively identified, with their presence detected at six of nine stations, and individual call sequences identified at two additional stations. EchoClass also identified the presence of big brown bats and Indiana bats, with a probability of mis-identification of $p < 0.01$. Two individual call sequences identified as tricolored bat calls were recorded at stations NOR1 and STU1. No other species were identified as present using EchoClass software (i.e. little brown bat, northern long-eared bat, small-footed bat). Table 4 displays the results of this analysis.

Species Presence – Kaleidoscope Pro

Kaleidoscope Pro software identified all three long-distance migratory bats (eastern red bats, silver-haired bats, hoary bats) as present at stations on Nantucket, with a probability that these species were mis-identified of $p < 0.00001$. Red bats were again the most commonly identified bat species, with its presence positively identified at seven of nine stations, and with an additional 41 probable calls identified at one additional station. Silver-haired bats were positively identified at six stations, with low numbers of calls identified at two additional stations. Hoary bats were positively identified at four stations, covering three of the five sites. A total of 60 calls were identified as big brown bat calls, but given the presence of other species that could be confused with these bats, this was not deemed sufficient to determine big brown bat presence. Similarly, seven tricolored bat calls were not sufficient to determine presence of this bat.

Kaliedoscope Pro software also positively identified the presence of three *Myotis* species on the island ($p < 0.00001$). Northern long-eared bats were positively identified at Norwood and Stump Pond stations. Small-footed and Indiana bats were also positively identified at the Stump Pond site, with two additional Indiana bat calls recorded elsewhere. Individual call sequences described as little brown bat calls were recorded at Squam Farm and Stump Pond, but these were not considered sufficient to determine presence. Table 5 displays the results of this analysis.

Species Identification – Manual Vetting

Big Brown Bat (*Eptesicus fuscus*) – As described previously, it can be difficult to differentiate calls of this species from those of the silver-haired bat, which produces calls in the same frequency range. Several feeding buzzes produced by this species were identified at the Gibbs Pond site on 5 and 6 September (Trevor Peterson, personal communication). In the same period, on 5 September, there were highly curvilinear calls at Stump Pond, which were identified by both auto and manual classification as big brown bat calls. In addition, a number of calls throughout the season were auto-classified by EchoClass and Kaliedoscope as big brown bats. However, most of these identifications occurred during periods of high silver-haired bat activity, so it is difficult to be sure that these were big brown bat calls.

Eastern Red Bat (*Lasiurus borealis*) – This bat was recorded sporadically at Medouie Creek from 21 May throughout the summer to 2 September. Calls were more common in mid-late September, from 11 September to 27 September, with the latest calls recorded on 5 and 6 October. Norwood Farm also showed sporadic activity throughout the season, from 13 May to 5 November. At Squam Farm, there was some activity in late May, no activity in June or July, and calls recorded on 15 August. Activity increased in October, with a peak of activity on 25 October, and continued calls recorded through 3 November. At Stump Pond, there was consistent activity from 6 June to 21 October, with particular peaks of activity on 31 August, 4 September, and 11 September. At Gibbs Farm, calls were recorded on 6, 7, and 16 October. A qualitative analysis of auto-classified calls of this species did not reveal any patterns or distinct peaks in activity.

Hoary Bat (*Lasiurus cinereus*) – Hoary bats were identified from sporadic individual calls at Norwood Farm on 12 August, several dates in late August, and at Medouie Creek on 28 August. The bat was also recorded at Medouie Creek from 10 September to 13 October. The bat was recorded at Stump Pond throughout August, and from 2 September to 21 September. No clear calls of this bat were identified at Squam Farm or Gibbs Pond. A qualitative analysis of auto-classified calls of this species did not reveal any patterns or distinct peaks in activity.

Silver-Haired Bat (*Lasionycteris noctivagans*) – This bat was recorded on 22 June at Norwood Farm, but was otherwise not detected until much later in the season. At this site, there was a peak of activity on 14 September. The bat was also recorded at this site on 28 August, 1 September, 16-18 September, 16 October, and 4 November. At Medouie Creek, there were peaks of activity for this species from 27-30 August. The bat was also present 14-19 September, 16, 20, and 31 of October, and 2 and 4 of November. At Stump Pond, this bat was recorded 23 and 29 July, and picked up sporadically through August. From 27-29 August, there was a great deal of activity. The bat was picked up sporadically from 30 August to 11 September. In mid-September, there was again a peak in activity on 15 September, with activity continuing into 18 and 19 September. Sporadic activity continued through 9 October, with a probable call recorded on 22 October. At Squam Farm, there was activity on 30 October, and a burst of activity on 5 November. At Gibbs Pond, calls were recorded on 2 November. Unlike other species, this bat appeared to come through in distinct waves, common across sites (Figures 2a and 2b).

Myotis Species (*Myotis spp.*) – *Myotis* spp. calls were identified at all five sites on Nantucket. *Myotis* calls were picked up at Medouie Creek in May, June and August, and at Norwood Farm from mid-May through mid-September. At Squam Farm, they were present from early May through early November. At Stump Pond, there were very high numbers of calls at the beginning of the study, particularly on 30 April, and continuing through early-mid-May, but *Myotis* were present throughout the season into early September. At Gibbs Pond, calls were recorded sporadically in the fall, on 6 September, and 6, 7, 11, and 21 October. Steeply sloped calls, characteristic of northern long-eared bats, were recorded at Norwood Farm, Squam Farm, and Stump Pond. Other *Myotis* spp. may have been present on Nantucket, but calls auto-classified as these species were not of sufficient quality to definitively identify them manually. Some lower-slope calls could have been *M. lucifugus* or *M. sodalis*, for example, but recordings contained too much echo and clutter to distinguish them from eastern red bat calls.

Tricolored Bat (*Perimyotis subflavus*) – As described previously, calls of this bat can be difficult to differentiate from those of eastern red bats, which means it may be under-represented in identification of calls to species. Both auto and manual classification identified one clear call sequence from Gibbs Pond on 21 October as this species. This identification was reviewed by an

expert (Trevor Peterson). Two calls at Norwood Farm on 15 May were identified as the tricolored bat by both EchoClass and manual classification, although Kaliedoscope identified the calls as those of an eastern red bat. Two calls from Stump Pond on 11 September were also auto-classified as the tricolored bat. These calls were somewhat cluttered, but did appear to be those of the tricolored bat.

Other Survey Methods

Efforts to elicit reports of bat sightings from local residents resulted in very little response. However, during the course of the study, a dead bat was brought to Nantucket Conservation Foundation staff by a resident. The bat was found near Johns Point on the western side of Nantucket (41.271954, -70.134437). This specimen was identified as a northern long-eared bat (*Myotis septentrionalis*) by the author. This identification was further confirmed by Jonathan Reichard, National White-Nose Syndrome Assistant Coordinator for the U.S. Fish & Wildlife; however, the bat was somewhat mauled and a genetic test would be definitive.

The Maria Mitchell Foundation has five bat specimens in its collection, including two silver-haired bats, two eastern red bats, and one hoary bat (Andrew McKenna-Foster, personal communication). These specimens confirm the presence of migratory tree bats on in the island in the late 1950s-1970s.

DISCUSSION

This is the first known inventory of bat species on Nantucket. All three long-distance migratory bat species - the hoary bat, silver-haired bat, and eastern red bat - were recorded on the island, at multiple sites. In addition, I documented the presence of *Myotis* species on Nantucket, including the federally threatened northern long-eared bat. The big brown bat and tricolored bat were also recorded. Small numbers of calls of these latter two species are more likely related to issues of species identification, rather than to low activity of these bats on the island.

The presence of long-distance migratory bats on Nantucket is not surprising given evidence suggesting their use of coastal areas along the Eastern Seaboard (Peterson et al. 2014), and their utilization of islands as stopover sites (e.g. Cryan and Brown 2007, Johnson et al. 2011). Specimens in the Maria Mitchell Foundation from the 1950-1970s suggest their presence is not a new phenomenon. Detections of hoary bats on the island are consistent with the idea that these bats visit the island during their fall migration. Calls of this species were recorded from mid-August to mid-October, but not earlier in the season.

Except for an individual call sequence on 22 June, silver-haired bat recordings were also consistent with presence during fall migration. These bats were recorded sporadically from late July through August at Stump Pond. At this and other sites, the bats were also recorded from the end of August to early November. Previous studies have often described peaks of migratory activity in which high capture rates in mist-nets, bats roosting in visible numbers, or high numbers of calls, indicate waves of migration, possibly associated with favorable weather conditions (e.g. Cryan 2003, Cryan and Brown 2007, Divoll 2012, McGuire et al. 2012, Peterson et al. 2014). Recordings on Nantucket supported this migratory pattern for the silver-haired bat, with peaks of activity that spanned multiple sites around 27-30 August, and again 14-19 September (Figures 2a and 2b). Meteorological data from the Citizen Weather Observer Station in eastern Nantucket (MesoWest 2015) shows midnight temperatures in the 15-20° C range, with winds 2-4 m/s from the west-northwest. A qualitative analysis showed temperatures and wind speeds on nights of high silver-haired bat activity did not appear to be significantly different from weather on surrounding nights. More exploration is needed to understand what may have prompted peaks of migration on the above dates, but silver-haired bats certainly appeared to be active in the region at this time. This species was also captured in mist-netting efforts on neighboring Tuckernuck Island around 14-15 September (Richard Veit, personal communication).

In contrast to the other two migratory tree bats, eastern red bats appear to be summer residents on some parts of Nantucket, in addition to being present during the migratory season. Eastern red bats first appeared on recordings in mid-May, and last were detected in early November. At Medouie Creek and Norwood Farm sites, these bats were detected sporadically throughout the

season. At Stump Pond, they were common throughout the season, with definite detection on 37% of nights between 6 June and 21 October. Their presence is consistent with analyses of museum specimen collections showing red bats in New England throughout the warmer months (Cryan 2003), and acoustic detection in Massachusetts during this time (e.g. Brooks 2011). Cryan (2003) identified both sexes moving into this region in the summer, meaning that maternity colonies may be present on Nantucket.

The presence of northern long-eared bats on Nantucket is in some sense unexpected, given the lack of heavy forest cover commonly associated with this species (MassWildlife 2015). However, increasing evidence suggests that these species will use houses and other structures as roost sites, even in areas where tree roosts are available. On neighboring Martha's Vineyard, these small-bodied bats often use the rake board, along the eaves of houses, as a roosting location, both for individuals and maternity colonies (Johnson et al. 2016). Given the profusion of houses with cedar shakes and trim on Nantucket, northern long-eared bats may well be utilizing this habitat. The question remains whether these bats are hibernating on-island, or migrating to mainland hibernacula. The continued presence of northern long-eared bats on Martha's Vineyard, Long Island, and Cape Cod (Curry 2016), in contrast to sharp population declines inland, has given rise to the theory that these bats may be hibernating locally, and experiencing less exposure to WNS. In February of this year, a healthy northern long-eared bat was found roosting under a rake board on Martha's Vineyard, supporting the idea that bats may be hibernating locally (Luanne Johnson, personal communication). If this is the case, Nantucket may be acting as a refugium for this threatened bat, as well as other WNS-affected species.

Auto-classifier identification of Indiana bat calls is intriguing, but it must be remembered that these software programs are prone to error, especially for recordings with a good deal of clutter or echo. Manual vetting of auto-classified calls by experts did not identify any definitive *Myotis sodalis* calls. The last known observation of the Indiana Bat in Massachusetts was in 1939 (NHESP 2012b), and the bat has not been found in neighboring Connecticut in the past 40 years (Jonathan Reichard, personal communication). Formerly, the species was known to hibernate at sites in Berkshire and Hampden counties of Massachusetts (NHESP 2012b). This finding warrants further investigation, but is unlikely that the species is present on the island, since

northern long-eared bat or little brown bat calls could easily be confused with those of the Indiana bat. The presence of little brown bats and eastern small-footed bats can also not be confirmed without a follow-up study. Mist-netting efforts at one or more sites on Nantucket would be informative, allowing for accurate identification of *Myotis* species “in the hand.” Future studies could also document habitat of northern long-eared bats and other WNS-affected species on the island, determine whether eastern red bats are maintaining summer maternity colonies, or explore patterns of migratory bat activity in the late summer-fall season.

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TABLES AND FIGURES

Table 1 - Description of acoustic detector locations

Table 2 – Acoustic detector deployment data

Table 3 – Auto-classifier comparison

Table 4 – EchoClass results

Table 5 – Kaleidoscope results

Figure 1 - Map of sites on island

Figure 2 – Patterns of silver-haired bat activity

Figure 3 – Photos of *Myotis septentrionalis* specimen

Site Location	Station Code	Latitude	Longitude	Height (m)	Site Description
Gibbs Farm	GIBBS	41.27618	-70.017873	1	scrub oak edge of large kettlehole pond, near active cranberry bog and some hardwood forest
Medouie Creek	MED1	41.30811	-70.01204	1.25	scrub/treeline on edge of salt marsh, bordering Polpis Harbor
Medouie Creek	MED2	41.30676	-70.01435	1.75	scrub edge of brackish marsh, surrounded by mature forested wetlands (tupelo, sassafras, red maple) and shrub swamp bordering Polpis Harbor
Norwood Farm	NOR1	41.28572	-70.01485	1.75	small kettle pond surrounded by scrub oak shrubland, some recently brush-cut
Norwood Farm	NOR2	41.28806	-70.01557	1	forest edge in mosaic of open fields, scrub oak, and hardwood forest near wetland
Squam Farm	SQU1	41.30962	-70.00006	2	hardwood forest edge by open grazed field, sassafras stand
Squam Farm	SQU2	41.3114	-69.99821	1.5	clearing in hardwood forest, among sassafras and oak
Stump Pond	STU1	41.2925	-70.00208	3	scrub oak edge of large pond, surrounded by mature hardwood forest
Stump Pond	STU2	41.29411	-70.00262	2	tree about 5m from scrub oak wetland in field surrounded by mosaic of hardwood forest and open fields

Table 1 Description of acoustic detector locations.

Station code	Dates deployed	Total nights deployed	Nights monitored (% of deployed)	Noisy nights	Total bat calls	Nights with bats	Average calls per night
GIBBS	8/25/2015 - 11/13/2015	80	69 (86%)	14	93	13 (24%)	1.69
MED1	4/29/2015 - 11/13/2015	198	118 (60%)	4	161	40 (35%)	1.41
MED2	4/30/2015 - 11/13/2015	197	173 (88%)	7	419	49 (30%)	2.52
NOR1	4/30/2015 - 11/13/2015	197	197 (100%)	13	551	102 (55%)	2.99
NOR2	4/30/2015 - 11/13/2015	197	165 (84%)	0	691	119 (72%)	4.19
SQU1	4/29/2015 - 11/13/2015	198	164 (83%)	18	755	49 (34%)	5.17
SQU2	4/29/2015 - 11/13/2015	114	114 (100%)	0	61	24 (21%)	0.54
STU1	4/30/2015 - 11/13/2015	197	167 (85%)	5	2821	136 (84%)	17.41
STU2	4/30/2015 - 11/13/2015	197	145 (74%)	9	286	67 (49%)	2.10
AVERAGE	-	174	146 (84%)	8	649	67 (45%)	4.23

Table 2 Acoustic detector deployment data.

Station code	Total bat calls	EchoClass Identified	Kaliedoscope Identified
GIBBS	93	5 (5.3%)	18 (19%)
MED1	161	7 (4.3%)	71 (44%)
MED2	419	84 (20%)	218 (52%)
NOR1	551	20 (3.6%)	257 (47%)
NOR2	691	4 (0.58%)	31 (4.5%)
SQU1	755	10 (1.3%)	68 (9.0%)
SQU2	61	0 (0%)	1 (1.6%)
STU1	2821	133 (4.7%)	789 (28%)
STU2	286	12 (4.1%)	16 (5.6%)
AVERAGE	649	31 (4.9%)	163 (23%)

Table 3 Auto-classifier comparison.

Site Code	EPFU	LABO	LACI	LANO	MYLE	MYLU	MYSE	MYSO	PESU
GIB1	call sequence (1 call)	call sequence (3 calls)	-	-	-	-	-	call sequence (1 call)	-
MED1	call sequence (1 call)	p <0.0001 (5 calls)	call sequence (1 call)	-	-	-	-	-	-
MED2	p <0.0001 (17 calls)	p <0.0001 (28 calls)	p <0.0001 (10 calls)	p <0.01 (30 calls)	-	-	-	-	-
NOR1	-	p <0.0001 (19 calls)	-	-	-	-	-	-	call sequence (1 call)
NOR2	-	call sequence (4 calls)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
SQU1	-	p <0.0001 (10 calls)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
SQU2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
STU1	call sequence (3 calls)	p <0.0001 (111 calls)	p <0.01 (15 calls)	call sequence (2 calls)	-	-	-	p <0.0001 (2 calls)	call sequence (1 call)
STU2	-	p <0.0001 (15 calls)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 4 EchoClass results. If a species was positively identified at a station on any night, the smallest p-value recorded is displayed. If only single call sequences were detected, “call sequence” is written, followed by a number indicating the number of nights on which a single call sequence was detected. A “-“ indicates lack of presence. EPFU=*Eptesicus fuscus*, big brown bat; LABO=*Lasiurus borealis*, eastern red bat; LACI=*Lasiurus cinereus*, hoary bat; LANO=*Lasionycteris noctivagans*, silver-haired bat; MYLE=*Myotis leibii*, eastern small-footed bat; MYLU=*Myotis lucifugus*, little brown bat; MYSE=*Myotis septentrionalis*, northern long-eared bat; MYSO=*Myotis sodalis*, Indiana bat; PESU=*Perimyotis subflavus*, tricolored bat.

Site Code	EPFU	LABO	LACI	LANO	MYLE	MYLU	MYSE	MYSO	PESU
GIB1	p=0.92 (2 calls)	p<0.00001 (6 calls)	-	p<0.0001 (8 calls)	-	-	-	p=0.068 (1 call)	p=0.39 (1 call)
MED1	p=1 (4 calls)	p<0.00001 (9 calls)	p=0.27 (2 calls)	p<0.00001 (56 calls)	-	-	-	-	-
MED2	p=1 (20 calls)	p<0.00001 (46 calls)	p<0.00001 (17 calls)	p<0.00001 (130 calls)	-	-	p=0.15 (1 call)	-	p=0.15 (4 calls)
NOR1	p=1 (4 calls)	p=1 (41 calls)	p<0.0001 (192 calls)	p=1 (14 calls)	-	-	p<0.00001 (5 calls)	p=0.59 (1 call)	-
NOR2	p=1 (1 call)	p<0.00001 (12 calls)	p=0.038 (2 calls)	p<0.00001 (16 calls)	-	-	-	-	-
SQU1	p=0.74 (9 calls)	p<0.00001 (18 calls)	p=0.74 (1 call)	p<0.00001 (39 calls)	-	p=1 (1 call)	-	-	-
SQU2	-	-	p=1 (1 call)	-	-	-	-	-	-
STU1	p=1 (20 calls)	p<0.00001 (266 calls)	p<0.00001 (29 calls)	p<0.00001 (452 calls)	p=0.0057 (3 calls)	p=1 (11 calls)	-	p=0.00001 (6 calls)	p=1 (2 calls)
STU2	-	p<0.00001 (7 calls)	-	p=1 (3 calls)	-	-	p<0.00001 (6 calls)	-	-

Table 5 Kaleidoscope results. If a species was identified at a station the p-value associated with presence is displayed. The number of calls identified as this species is also recorded. A “-“ indicates lack of presence. EPFU=*Eptesicus fuscus*, big brown bat; LABO=*Lasiurus borealis*, eastern red bat; LACI=*Lasiurus cinereus*, hoary bat; LANO=*Lasionycteris noctivagans*, silver-haired bat; MYLE=*Myotis leibii*, eastern small-footed bat; MYLU=*Myotis lucifugus*, little brown bat; MYSE=*Myotis septentrionalis*, northern long-eared bat; MYSO=*Myotis sodalis*, Indiana bat; PESU=*Perimyotis subflavus*, tricolored bat.

Figure 1 Map of acoustic detector sites on Nantucket (courtesy of NCF).

Figure 2a Patterns of silver-haired bat activity by week, from first to last detection in 2015. Sums of silver-haired bat calls as identified by Kaliedoscope. Note peaks at multiple sites around weeks 35-36 and week 38.

Figure 2b Patterns of silver-haired bat activity by day, 15 July to 5 November 2015. Sums of silver-haired bat calls as identified by Kaliedoscope. Note peaks in late August and mid-September.

Figure 3 Photographs of *Myotis septentrionalis* specimen found on Nantucket, with narrow tragus characteristic of this species.